

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	--------------

SJABLOON VALIDATIEPLAN NFI

Title

Validation of IC-ESI-MS method for the identification and quantification of low molecular weight anions related to pyrotechnics and inorganic explosives in casework samples.

Identificatie van het validatierapport	17CFS302 – Pyroprof project (MSCA N. 747249), 25/06/2018 Divisie Chemische & Fysische Sporen Team E&E
Betrokken medewerkers	Carlos Martín Alberca Jacinta Jansen Chris-Jan Kuijpers Mattijs Koeberg Annemieke Hulsbergen Leonie Uittenbogaart Jesse Verbunt Inge Ekkelenkamp
Auteur	Carlos Martín Alberca
Schaduw	Jacinta Jansen and Chris-Jan Kuijpers
Autorisator	Mattijs Koeberg
Uitvoerend onderzoeker(s)	Carlos Martín Alberca Chris-Jan Kuijpers

Geprint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 1/18
--------------------------	--	-----------

1 Introduction

Until 2018 at the NFI's Explosive and Explosion Section, an analytical screening method (described in QOL00863) is applied to determine the ion (anions and cations) composition of aqueous extracts of casework samples related to inorganic explosives and pyrotechnic items (e.g. fireworks) [1]. This QOL00863 method is able to separate and detect 8 anions (i.e., chloride, chlorate, perchlorate, sulfate, thiocyanate, nitrite, nitrate and phosphate) and 8 cations within 45 minutes. This method is based on a chromatographic separation by an Ion Chromatography (IC) instrument coupled to two relatively non-specific detectors [2]; a conductivity detector and an UV-detector. The result of the current method gives a qualitative indication for the presence of the mentioned ions, because of its relatively low selectivity/specificity, in addition to quantitative information. Therefore, in order to improve the analytical methodology applied to this kind of samples, a new mass spectrometry (MS) detector with electrospray ionization (ESI) will be used, coupled to an IC as a complementary and more selective method for full identification and quantification of anions. This MS, a single quadrupole, is a more specific detector that allows to identify and quantify characteristic ion fragments with high precision and sensitivity [2]. Additionally, an on-line suppressed conductivity detector will be placed between the IC-instrument and the MS detector.

The IC-ESI-MS method will serve for the accurate and sensitive quantification of 22 low-mass anions in samples with a variety of matrices related to post-explosion forensic casework samples of pyrotechnic and inorganic explosives. The list of anions of interest (see **Table 1**) includes common low-weight inorganic anions and selected organic acids that usually appear in or are related to this sort of casework. This validation plan for an in-house validation (single laboratory study) is set up in order to demonstrate if the performance characteristics of the IC-ESI-MS method are adequate for use for this particular purpose.

Table 1. The following anions of interest will be obtained from this list of salts or reagents.

Analytes	Obtained from
Azide	Sodium azide
Benzoate	Potassium benzoate
Bromate	Sodium bromate
Bromide	Sodium bromide

Chlorate	Potassium chlorate
Chloride	Sodium chloride
Chromate	Sodium chromate
Cyanate	Sodium cyanate
Formate	Calcium formate
Iodate	Potassium iodate
Iso-phthalate	Iso-phthalic acid / Benzene-1,3- dicarboxylic acid
Nitrate	Potassium nitrate
Nitrite	Sodium nitrite
Oxalate	Oxalic acid
Perchlorate	Potassium perchlorate
Phosphate	Disodium phosphate
Phthalate	o-Phthalic acid / Benzene-1,2- dicarboxylic acid
Sulfate	Sodium sulphate
Tartrate	Tartaric acid
Therephthate	Therephthalic acid / Benzene-1,4- dicarboxylic acid
Thiocyanate	Potassium thiocyanate
Thiosulfate	Potassium thiosulfate

2 Methods and materials

- *Reagents, standards, validation samples and real samples:*

- Acetonitrile (ACN), isopropanol and methanol will be purchased from Biosolve BV (Valkenswaard, The Netherlands), ACN, sulfuric acid, and sodium bicarbonate from Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands), and sodium carbonate from Honeywell-Fluka - Fisher Scientific (Landsmeer, The Netherlands). All reagents are of analytical grade ($\geq 98\%$), and they will be used throughout this validation process. Milli-Q grade water (ultrapure water) of $18.2 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}^{-1}$ will be used for preparing mobile phases, suppressor eluents,

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	--------------

measurement stock standards, reagents blanks and test samples, as well as for rinsing the Autosampler system and for preparing the MS cleaning eluents.

- The 22 anions of interest will be obtained from their corresponding inorganic salt or chemical compound (see **Table 1**), obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands). From them, measurement stock standards/calibrators will be prepared at 1000 mg/L aqueous solution (i.e., in ultrapure water), except for iso-phthalate, which will be prepared at 100 mg/L due to its lower solubility in water [3]. In addition, based on these measurement stock standards/calibrators, reagent blanks containing all 22 anions will be prepared at several concentrations from 0.0005 µg/mL to 25 µg/mL (see section 4 for more information).

- Twelve matrices of interest in this type of casework will be used in the validation process: blood, rubber, metal, cotton, swab (alcohol pads 70% isopropyl alcohol, purchased from B. Braun Medical BV, Oss, The Netherlands), soil, plastic, cardboard, soot, rust, tile and tire.

- *Analytical instrumentation:*

- A Metrohm 919 IC Autosampler plus.
- A Metrohm 850 Professional IC equipped with a Metrohm Metrosep A Trap 1 column (100 x 4.0 mm) combined with a Metrosep A Supp 5 anion-exchange column (250 x 4.0 mm). The sample loop is 20 µL.
- A Metrohm IC Professional Conductivity detector.
- A 3-step column suppressor (Metrohm MSM Rotor A).
- A Waters® SQ detector 2 instrument, equipped with a single quadrupole. The ion source is a Z-Spray ESI.
- Additionally, one of the high pressure pumps of a Waters® UPLC ACQUITY Binary Solvent Manager instrument will be use to implement an automatic post-column rinsing method. This rinsing step will keep clean the MS interphase, and it will be run during the last part of each single analysis (during the IC column re-equilibration step).

- *Analytical method:*

- Two different mobile phases made up of 34% (A) and 10% (B) ACN in ultrapure water and containing 5 mM sodium carbonate and 4.8 mM sodium bicarbonate.

Geprint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 4/18
--------------------------	--	-----------

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	--------------

- The IC will be used in stepwise gradient mode at a constant flow of 0.8 mL/min and column temperature of 30°C. First, eluent B will be pumped with a high pressure pump at 100% during 11.20 min. Then, a stepwise gradient ramp will be applied for 4.50 min (total run time 15.70 min). From then on, the eluent A will be pumped at 100% up to 30 min. Then a re-equilibration step for 30 min will be applied. This last step consist of flushing the eluent B again with a high pressure pump at 100%.

- Two suppressor liquids made with 50 mM solution of sulphuric acid in ultrapure water (A) and a 30%:70% (v:v) ACN in ultrapure water (B).

- The eluent coming into the MS interphase will be split 70% to the waste and 30% to the MS (split mode). This will be done in order to avoid suppression effects on the signal recorded by the instrument (i.e., high concentration of analytes coming into the MS). For that, two PEEK tubes (yellow PEEK of 70-80 cm directed to waste, and red PEEK of 20 cm coming into the MS) will be set in a T-piece.

- The MS instrument will be operated in negative (ESI-) mode. Specific mases in the range 20.00 to 500.00 m/z (see section 4 for more information) will be monitored by selected ion recording (SIR) mode, at different cone voltages. Three additional full scan channels (i.e., MS scan mode) at different cone voltages (i.e., 10 V, 50 V and 90 V) will be set in continuum for scanning the entire spectrum looking for ions produced by unknown compounds.

- The MS interphase rinse eluent consist of 20% isopropanol in ultrapure water (v/v). This will be infused into the MS interphase at a flow rate of 0.2 mL/min during 25 min (running parallel to the re-equilibration step).

- *Data acquisition*

- All data acquisition will be performed using MagIC Net Professional version 3.1. software from Metrohm and MassLynx™ version 4.1. software from Waters.

3 Type of method

The type of analytical procedure to be validated is a **new qualitative and quantitative** method for the identification of low molecular weight anions present in samples related to inorganic explosive and pyrotechnic casework (i.e., water extracts obtained from post-explosion samples).

Chapter: Customer requirements

Gepreint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 5/18
---------------------------	--	-----------

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	--------------

The results of the described method will typically be used to help relate samples from a crime scene to the use of (a particular type of) inorganic explosive material/mixture. In post-explosion cases typically only small amounts of residues of the original explosive charge will be present in samples taken. In order to do this the method must be able to detect and identify these residues in aqueous extracts of samples, at microgram per milliliter levels (as present on/in the sample), in commonly encountered matrices. In order to deduce relationships between identified ions in the complex aqueous mixtures obtained, the quantification must be accurate within at least one order of magnitude. The level of identification certainty must be to accepted standards, or better. In order to obtain a validated analytical method that fits for the forensic explosive trace analysis, the international recognized standards will be followed [4, 5].

4 Performance characteristics

The performance characteristics to be verified for the new qualitative and quantitative method will be:

- **Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ):**

The detection limits of this new method and this instrument (i.e., conductivity and MS detectors) will be measured for each analyte. The background noise of the detectors during a single separation will be compared to the obtained signals (i.e., peaks) from test samples (i.e. swabs) and reagent blanks containing concentrations of the different analytes, close to or below the expected LODs [4]. The estimated instrument LODs for each analyte are shown in **Table 2**. The chosen measuring strategy is known as Signal-to-Noise (S/N) ratio, and it will be measured using the available tools offered in the above-mentioned MagIC and MaxxLynx software. The following equation will be used:

$$\text{Signal-to-Noise} = \text{height of analyte} / \text{amplitude of noise}$$

Conductivity and MS signals will be considered as a peak for the LOD if it is 3 times higher than the noise of the detector [4], and for the LOQ if it is minimum 10 times higher than the noise of the detector [4]. The standard deviation have to be also calculated (S_0) [4].

Reagent blanks including each of the analytes of interest at relevant concentrations will be used for calculating the instrument LODs and LOQs. Those complex standards containing the 22 anions will be prepared at concentrations x0.2, x0.5, x0.9, x1, x1.1, x2, where the lower expected LOD will be the

Gepreint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 6/18
---------------------------	--	-----------

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	--------------

reference (i.e., x1) (see **Table 2**). Each complex standard will be prepared 10 times, and analyzed 1 time each solution. Expected overlapped ions (tartrate and sulfate, and azide and nitrate) might be studied separately in order to evaluate the conductivity detection parameters.

In addition, test samples will be analyzed for obtaining the method LODs and LOQs. In this case, non-spiked swabs and spiked swabs with the reagent blanks will be measured. First, 10 non-spiked swabs will be extracted using the sample preparation protocol (i.e., NFI SOP 161501 [6]) and analyzed by triplicated. Second, three set of 10 swabs will be spiked with three relevant concentrations. One of those concentration have to be the estimated instrumental LOD (x1), and the other two should be concentrations above that LOD (x1.5 and x2). Each extracted sample will be analyzed one time. In addition, expected overlapped ions (tartrate and sulfate, and azide and nitrate) might be studied separately in order to evaluate the conductivity detection parameters.

Then, the minimum concentration at which the analyte of interest can be reliably detected and quantified by this method (i.e. with acceptable retention time, peak shape, mass spectral ion ratios; see below the rest of the performance characteristics) will be established.

Table 2. Expected instrument LODs for the analytes of interest at the conductivity and MS detectors, and their corresponding expected intervals.

Analytes	Expected LODs – Conductivity detector (µg/mL)	Expected LODs – MS detector (µg/mL)	Expected interval – Conductivity detector (µg/mL)	Expected interval – MS detector (µg/mL)
Azide	n.i.	1	n.i.	3 - 5
Benzoate	0.01	0.01	0.1 – 20	0.04 - 25
Bromate	0.01	0.01	0.1 – 20	0.04 - 5
Bromide	-	-	-	-
Chlorate	0.01	0.01	0.1 – 20	0.04 - 5
Chloride	0.001	0.01	0.1 – 20	0.04 - 10
Chromate	0.001	0.01	0.1 – 20	0.04 - 5
Cyanate	0.1	0.1	0.1 – 20	0.3 - 5
Formate	0.01	0.01	0.1 – 20	0.1 - 25
Iodate	n.i.	0.01	n.i.	0.04 - 10

Geprint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 7/18
--------------------------	--	-----------

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	--------------

Iso-phthalate	0.01	0.01	0.1 – 20	0.04 - 25
Nitrate	0.01	0.01	0.1 – 20	0.04 - 20
Nitrite	0.1	0.1	0.4 – 2	0.5 - 20
Oxalate	0.01	0.01	0.1 – 1	0.04 - 10
Perchlorate	0.1	0.01	0.1 – 20	0.04 - 5
Phosphate	0.1	0.05	0.1 – 20	0.1 - 10
Phthalate	0.1	0.01	0.1 – 20	0.04 - 10
Sulfate	n.i.	0.01	n.i.	0.04 - 10
Tartrate	n.i.	0.1	n.i.	0.05 - 5
Therephlathate	-	-	-	-
Thiocyanate	0.1	0.01	0.1 -20	0.04 - 5
Thiosulfate	0.1	0.01	0.1 – 2	0.04 - 5

n.i.= no info because those peaks appear overlapped on the conductivity chromatogram.

- **Selectivity / specificity:**

First, the retention time, and the chromatographic resolution at the conductivity detector (baseline separation), of critical compounds among the ions of interest (those included in **Table 1**) will be checked. Critical compounds are those that could be misidentified due to them sharing characteristics diagnostic ions when eluting at the same retention time. In this case, phosphate and sulfate, and azide and cyanate will be checked. Additionally, the ion fragmentation and ion-ratio of each compound of interest will be also studied after the analysis of a high concentration (i.e., 100 ppm) of each measurement standard/calibrator. The information obtained will serve to complete/correct the theoretical diagnostic ions and isotope abundances collected in **Table 3**. This experiment will also help to detect any additional false positives when using the ion fragments in the identification.

Secondly, specificity/selectivity will be also verified by deliberately selecting and analyzing potential interfering substances (i.e., isomers, isobaric species, degradation products) that could lead to a false positive. For example, the three isomers of phthalic acid have already been included as compounds of interest in this study (see **Table 1**). They will be analyzed, and their retention times and main characteristic ions will checked. Additional compounds will be explored. For instance, lactate shares diagnostic ions with the analyte of interest oxalate, hence lactate will be checked. Then, relevant test samples (i.e., matrices) will be

Geprint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 8/18
--------------------------	--	-----------

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	-----------

verified in order to identify additional potential interfering substances. Extracts from twelve non-spiked matrices of interest will be analyzed: blood, rubber, metal, cotton, swab, soil, plastic, cardboard, soot, rust, tile and tire. Then, they will be fortified/spiked at a relevant and known concentration (this concentration depends on the range study's results) with the measurement standard/calibrators that have been stipulated as possible interfering substances with the identification and quantification of the target ions.

The effect of each detected interference over the region of interest, where the target analytes are expected to elute, will be investigated. In case of notable influence on quantification and/or false positive risk –this is, the impossibility of getting enough evidence of its identity with a minimum of identification points or in case of high chances of false-positive (i.e., $\alpha = 0.05$) [5]–, further method development will be implemented. In order to evaluate this: (1) the (relative) retention time will be taken into account as an identification point. For the purpose of assuring the correct measurement of time, it will be studied the use of a stable system peak. The (relative) retention time ratio should have a tolerance of $\pm 2.5\%$ [5], and the minimum acceptable retention time is twice the retention time corresponding to the void volume of the column [5]. And (2), the rest of the identification points will be taken from diagnostic ions (e.g., molecular ion, product ion), and isotope-abundance analysis of main stable isotopes (i.e., **ion-ratio study**) detected by the MS detector. The theoretical diagnostic ions and isotope-abundances of the compounds of interest have been collected in **Table 3** together with an estimation of total number of identification points for each compound. The mentioned experiments will help to fill in/correct the remaining information. In addition, the relative intensity of the diagnostic ions should be more than 10% in the reference spectrum and agree with the criteria mentioned in **Table 4**, which is a partial reproduction of the *table 4* of the following reference [5].

Table 3. Number of identification points that can be earned by each analyte of interest based on their (relative) retention time, theoretical diagnostic ions and stable isotope-abundances.

Ion name and formula*	(Relative) Retention Time	Main ion	Main stable isotope ion within its ratio	Additional product ions	Maximum number of identification points
Azide - N_3^-	✓	42			2
Benzoate - $C_6H_5CO_2^-$	✓	121.	122 - ratio: 7.6		3

Geprint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 9/18
--------------------------	--	-----------

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	--------------

Bromate - BrO_3^-	✓	129	127 - ratio: 98.1		3
Bromide – Br^-	✓	81	79 - ratio: ??		3
Chlorate - ClO_3^-	✓	83	85 - ratio: 32.6	67 – ratio: ?	4
Chloride - Cl^-	✓	35	37 - ratio: 32.5		3
Chromate - CrO_4^{2-} / HCrO_4^-	✓	117	118 - ratio: 11.3 / 115 - ratio: 5.2		4
Cyanate - OCN^-	✓	42			2
Formate - HCO_2^-	✓	45			2
Iodate - IO_3^-	*	175		159, 143, 127	4
Isophthalate - $\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{O}_4^{2-}$ / $\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{O}_4^-$	✓	165	166 - ratio: 9		3
Nitrate - NO_3^-	✓	62		46 – ratio ??	3
Nitrite - NO_2^-	✓	46			2
Oxalate - $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ / HC_2O_4^-	✓	89	90 - ratio: 2.37		3
Perchlorate - ClO_4^-	✓	99	101 - ratio: 32.6	83	4
Phosphate - PO_4^{2-} / HPO_4^-	✓	97		79 - Ratio: ?	3
Phthalate - $\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{O}_4^{2-}$ / $\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{O}_4^-$	✓	165	166 - ratio: 9		3
Sulfate - SO_4^{2-} / HSO_4^-	✓	97	99 - ratio: 4.4	80 – ratio: ?	4
Tartrate - $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6^{2-}$ / $\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{O}_6^-$	✓	149	150 - ratio: 4.5	87, 73, 59	6
Terephthalate	✓	165	166 – ratio: 9	121	4

Geprint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 10/18
--------------------------	---	---------------

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	--------------

C₈H₄O₄²⁻ /
C₈H₅O₄⁻

Thiocyanate - SCN ⁻	✓	58	60 - ratio: 4.4	3
Thiosulfate - S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ / HS ₂ O ₃ ⁻	✓	113	115 - ratio: 8.8	3

* All ions are measured as -1.

Table 4. Maximum permitted tolerances for relative ion intensities using a range of Liquid Chromatography-MS technique. This table has been partially reproduced from [5].

Relative intensity (% of base peak)	LC-MS (relative)
> 50 %	± 20 %
> 20 % to 50 %	± 25 %
> 10 % to 20 %	± 30 %
≤ 10 %	± 50 %

- **Method and instrument working ranges (interval), and linearity**

The expected interval/range of interest spans from the LOQ of each analyte to upper end of the working range, i.e. those concentrations at which significant anomalies in the analytical sensitivity are observed [4], in this case to a maximum of around 25 ppm for some of the ions (see **Table 2**). There are two types of ranges that will be assessed: the method and the instrument working ranges.

In order to assess the instrument working range in both detectors, test samples (swabs) spiked at concentrations ± 20% of the expected interval, besides 8 additional concentrations evenly spaced across that range, will be used. Each sample will be prepared 3 times. They will be extracted using the sample preparation protocol (i.e., NFI SOP 161501 [6]) and analyzed one time. The plotting of the obtained data will give a visual confirmation (i.e. a response curve) of the linear range (or dynamic or quadratic) and of the upper and lower limits of the instrument working range. Then, the regression statistics and residual plot will be studied in order to confirm the relationship between concentration and instrument response. Correlation coefficient should be of R²

Geprint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 11/18
--------------------------	--	---------------

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	--------------

≥0.995. Finally, the proposed calibration procedure will be used for calibrating the instrument.

Next, the method working range will be defined. This can be done using the data obtained from the bias and precision studies (see below). If those data are not available in the range of interest, then test samples will be assessed in order to confirm that interference compounds or the extraction method are not causing other type of responses. The test samples will be spiked at 6-10 different concentrations, as described before, and then analyzed. This will be done in one time.

- **Quality of the results: bias/recovery (or “finite” trueness), and precision**

This section describes the quality of results obtained [4]. It expresses the closeness of a single obtained result to a true value. It will be determined studying two performance characteristics: recovery or bias, which is also known as “finite” trueness, and precision (or accuracy).

Firstly, bias/recovery will be studied through a recovery experiment, spiking test samples (i.e., the above mentioned matrices) with reagent blank at 3 different concentrations (low, medium and high), in replicates of 8 [7]. Low concentrations shall be approximately 3 times the lowest end of the working range of the method. High concentrations shall be within approximately 80% of the highest end of the working range of the method. Medium concentrations shall be near the midpoint of the low and high concentrations. Then, they will be extracted and measured, and compared with the results of un-spiked blank matrices. The relative spike recovery R' (%) will be calculated from the difference between the mean value of compound concentration obtained from spiked samples and the mean value from un-spiked samples, and divided by the added concentration (fortification level). As this term is a percentage, that value have to be multiplied by 100 [4].

$$\% = [\text{mean value spiked test samples} - \text{mean value un-spiked test samples} / \text{fortification level}] \times 100$$

This value should be within 80-120%. This should be done with both detectors. In addition, possible ion suppression or ion enhancement effect at the MS detector will be studied on those semi- and overlapped ions. This experiment will consist in analyze fixed concentration of one of the overlapped compounds together with the other overlapped compounds present in the same sample, but at variable concentration (e.g., nitrate/azide at concentrations w/w 1:0.1, 1:0.5

Gepreint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 12/18
---------------------------	--	---------------

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	--------------

or 1:0.9). The relative recovery values (%) will be compared in order to assess possible ion suppression or enhancement effects.

Secondly, precision is a measure of how close results are to one another [4]. Two measures of precision will be assessed:

- (1) Repeatability (within run precision and between run precision), specifically retention time and peak area repeatability.
- (2) And Intermediate precision (ruggedness) will be also assessed.

This study will be carried out as a single experiment following the instructions given in reference [4], applying one-way analysis of variation (ANOVA) [7-9]. Two analysts will prepare and analyze 6 reagent blanks each day during 5 days in a row at 3 different concentrations (low, medium and high). The first week of analysis each one of them will prepare and analyze every day the 6 reagent blanks at medium concentration. They will use different equipment (pipettes, flasks, etc.). The following two weeks, the analysts will analyze the samples at low and high concentrations. The mean, and the standard deviation or relative standard deviation (SD or RSD) will be assessed [7], and one-way ANOVA will be applied [8, 9]. Those coefficient of variation values for retention time should be within $\leq 5\%$ for each compound, and within $\leq 20\%$ for peak area. This equation should be applied:

$$\text{Coefficient of variation (\%)} = [\text{SD} / \text{mean}] \times 100$$

This experiment is also valid for the **ruggedness/robustness study** (see below).

- **Ruggedness / robustness**

This characteristic tries to identify the variables (e.g., analytical parameters, conditions or nominal values) which have the most significant effect when performing the method [4]. The close control of those variables will ensure its correct performance. The experiment for evaluating this will be based on the Plackett-Burman experimental design [10], using some test samples of interest (see **Table 5** and **Table 6**):

- As the mobile phase composition is critical in this kind of analytical method, the influence of some variations in its composition will be assessed:

1) the influence of variations in mobile phase composition will be assessed. Several mobile phases made with different concentrations of ACN ($\pm 2\%$) and sodium carbonate/sodium bicarbonate buffer will be made and then, the

Gepreint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 13/18
---------------------------	--	---------------

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	--------------

analytical results will be compared and, if necessary, a significance test will be carried out.

2) the influence of using different suppliers (this is different brands) of the main mobile phase compounds will be assessed. Several mobile phases made with different brands of ACN will be applied to the analysis of some test samples of interest, then the results compared, and, if necessary, a significance test will be carried out.

- The suppressor eluents could also influence in the detection of the analytes by conductivity, or even damage the MS detector. Therefore, the influence of some variations in their composition will be studied. It is important to keep in mind that the suppressor has three chambers and each one is refilled every 10 minutes, therefore the instrument should be run a minimum of 30 min before run a test modifying the suppressor eluent compositions:

1) the influence of sulphuric acid in the suppressor eluent A: 50 mM solution of sulphuric acid in ultrapure water, and 100% ultrapure water.

2) the influence of ACN concentration in the suppressor eluent B: 30%:70% (v:v) ACN in ultrapure water, and 100% ultrapure water.

- Column temperature influence will be also assessed. Different column temperature will be set during three consecutive runs in order to study its influence on the retention time and peak area.

- Mobile phase flow rate influence will be studied on the retention time and peak area of the analytes of interest. Flow rates at 0.6, 0.8 and 1 mL/min will be assessed.

- The chromatographic column re-equilibration step will be also assessed since a non-efficient re-equilibration of the column might affect to the next run, for instance, with carry-over of ions to the next analysis. Several re-equilibration times (25 and 30 min) will be tested. Five non-stop runs will be performed and the obtained retention times and peak areas from those 5 runs will be compared.

- As part of the carry-over effect evaluation during the robustness experiments, the ion source conditions (i.e., contamination) will be studied. A MS interphase (post-column) rinsing method will be implemented in this method to avoid carry-over of ions to the next analysis. During the validation process, the efficiency of this cleaning method will be assessed. The system will be run with and without using the MS cleaning method. Additionally, a part of this experimental design for evaluating the robustness, another carry-over study for the autosampler will be carried out. This possible effect will be studied after inject the highest calibrator concentration (25 ppm). The obtained signal should not exceed 10% of signal of lowest calibrator.

Gepreint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 14/18
---------------------------	--	---------------

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	--------------

Performance results of the 12 experiments (**Table 6**, from A to L) will be compared each other and evaluated. Additionally, the **intermediate precision** mentioned above will be also part of this study (i.e., influence of several analysts and measurements along several days).

Table 5. Analytical parameters to be evaluated and the normal and variation conditions.

Parameter	Normal condition (+)	Variation (-)
Suppressor eluent A	50 mM H ₂ SO ₄ in ultrapure water	100% ultrapure water
Suppressor eluent B	30%: 70% (v:v) ACN in ultrapure water	100% ultrapure water
Solvent concentration in mobile phase A	34%	32%
Solvent concentration in mobile phase B	10%	12%
Buffer concentration in mobile phase A	5/4.8 mM sodium carbonate/sodium bicarbonate	4.8/5 mM sodium carbonate/sodium bicarbonate
Buffer concentration in mobile phase B	5/4.8 mM sodium carbonate/sodium bicarbonate	4.8/5 mM sodium carbonate/sodium bicarbonate
Solvent supplier	Biosolve	Sigma-Aldrich
Column temperature	30 °C	25 °C
Flow rate	0.8 mL/min	0.6 mL/min
Re-equilibration time	30 min	25 min
MS source contamination	Using MS cleaning method	No MS cleaning method

Table 6. Factorial combinations of the analytical parameters for the study of robustness by Plackett-Burman experimental design [10].

Parameter	Combinations											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Suppressor eluent A	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
Suppressor eluent B	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-
Solvent concentration in	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-

Geprint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 15/18
--------------------------	--	---------------

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	--------------

mobile phase A												
Solvent concentration in mobile phase B	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	-	+
Buffer concentration in mobile phase A	+	-	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	-
Buffer concentration in mobile phase B	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+
Solvent supplier	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	+
Column temperature	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	+
Flow rate	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-
Re-equilibration time	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-
MS source contamination	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+
RESULTS	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L

- **Stability**

Stability of the calibrators in water solution and reagent blank during storage will be assessed. The standard solutions will be stored for several days/weeks (i.e., 48 hours, and one to four weeks) in the dark at different temperatures (i.e. -20, 4, and 20 °C). Some of the solutions stored at 20 °C will be also kept under natural light. First, the complex reagent blank will be study. Then, if necessary, the individual calibrators will be studied. The results will be given in % of analyte remaining, taken as 100% the analytes analyzed from the freshly prepared solution. The maximum degradation accepted will be 80% remaining. This experiment could be stopped at any time if we observe significant changes.

Geprint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 16/18
--------------------------	--	---------------

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	--------------

5 Tjpad

Activity	Performance by	Planned end date
Validatie plan opstellen (inclusief aanmaken labjournaalbladen, afstemming met betrokkenen) en accordering	Mattijs Koeberg	28-June-2018
Inventarisatie veiligheidsrisico's (PBM aanschaffen, instructies etc)		July-2018
Vastleggen afspraken leverancier t.a.v. prestatiekenmerken, validatiegegevens leverancier, onderhoud(scontract), aanspreekpunt leverancier, reactietijd bij problemen, inwerken mdw'ers etc.	Jacinta Jansen	Middel July-2018
Logboek apparatuur aanmaken (apparaat markeren nog niet gevalideerd en kalibratiestatus)	Chris-Jan Kuijpers	Middel July-2018
Gebruiksaanwijzingen, CD's etc. archiveren	Chris-Jan Kuijpers	Middel July-2018
Onderzoeksmateriaal verzamelen	Chris-Jan Kuijpers and Carlos Martin Alberca	First week July-2018
Uitvoeren validatieonderzoek	MLO student??, Jacinta Jansen, Leonie Uittenbogaart	Second week September 2018 on
Registratie van de locatie van het monstermateriaal (ruimte X of vernietigd)	Jacinta Jansen	
Opstellen documentatiemap (alle communicatie vastleggen, o.a. tussen afdelingen etc.)	Jacinta Jansen	
Back up regelen (bv ICT)	Jacinta Jansen and I.T.	July-2018
Opstellen validatierapport	Carlos Martin Alberca	October-2018
Accordering validatierapport	Mattijs Koeberg	November-2018
Opstellen implementatieplan	??	??
Uitvoeren interne check en evt. constatering verhelpen	??	??
Specifiek extra item voor validatie software etc	??	??
Communicatie met RVA	Mattijs Koeberg	December-2018

Geprint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 17/18
--------------------------	--	---------------

Formulier: QOL-02504	NFI Sjabloon Validatieplan	Versie: 4
-----------------------------	----------------------------	--------------

6 Autorisatie

Auteur

Schaduw

Autorisator

7 References

- [1] NFI internal document number QOL-00863.
- [2] L. Barron, E. Gilchrist; *Anal. Chim. Acta* 806 (2014) 27-54.
- [3] C.M. Park, R.J. Sheehan; *Kirk-Othmer Encyclopedia of Chemical Technology*. (1999-2011). New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons.
- [4] B. Magnusson, U. Örnemark (eds.); *Eurachem Guide: The Fitness for Purpose of Analytical Methods – A Laboratory Guide to Method Validation and Related Topics*, (2nd ed. 2014). ISBN 978-91-87461-59-0. Available from www.eurachem.org.
- [5] European Council Directive 96/23/EC.
- [6] NFI internal document number SOP 161501.
- [7] Environment - performance characteristics of measurement methods, NEN 7777: 2003 nl, 1 July 2003.
- [8] F.T. Peters, O.H. Drummer, F. Musshoff; *Forensic Sci. Int.* 165 (2007) 216–224.
- [9] Scientific Working Group for Forensic Toxicology (SWGTOX), *Standard Practices for Method Validation in Forensic Toxicology*, May 20, 2013.
- [10] W.J. Youden, E.H. Steiner; *Statistical Manual of the AOAC*, AOAC International, 1975, ISBN 0-935584-15-3.

Geprint op: 10/4/2019	NB: dit formulier is geldig tot een nieuwe versie in QOL is vrijgegeven.	Pag. 18/18
--------------------------	--	---------------